

Drivers of organizational citizenship behavior of elementary school teachers

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ABSTRACT

This study aims to examine the effect of self-efficacy, intrinsic motivation on organizational citizenship behavior (OCB) of elementary school teachers in the post-COVID-19 pandemic mediated by teacher engagement and moderated by job characteristics. A total of 285 valid questionnaires, were analyzed using Structural Equation Modeling with SmartPLS3 software. The results showed that teacher engagement mediates the effects of self-efficacy and intrinsic motivation on organizational citizenship behavior. Job characteristics moderate the effect of intrinsic motivation and self-efficacy on teacher engagement, where moderation in the relationship between intrinsic motivation and teacher engagement is positive, and the moderating role in the relationship between self-efficacy and teacher engagement is negative. This shows that the school must be able to encourage teachers to demonstrate OCB in the school environment, so that teachers are willing to help their students and colleagues deal with learning in the post-pandemic period, in addition to jobs that offer a high degree of autonomy, task variety, task significance, and feedback.

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1. INTRODUCTION

The COVID-19 pandemic has become endemic. Life has returned to normal and activity restrictions are decreasing. However, the teacher felt that students had not reached the learning target, because of past online learning. This is caused by a lack of teacher competence in carrying out online learning (in terms of methods, media, abilities, and time limitations), in addition to limitations originating from students (lack of equipment that supports online learning, lack of parental support in online learning) [1]. For this reason, teachers are required to show organizational citizenship behavior (OCB), namely the willingness to play an extra role. Organizational citizenship behavior describes behavior in which employees are willing to go beyond defined role requirements [2]–[6], contribute more to the process and success of the organization [7].

Bogler and Somech [8] investigated teacher OCB during the COVID-19 pandemic, and revealed that Israeli teachers reported more OCB during COVID-19 than before COVID-19, more to students, less to schools and parents, and least to colleagues. Bogler and Somech [8] identified six main categories that involve teacher action beyond the definition of their role: promoting academic achievement, expending more time, assisting students, usage of technology, compliance with COVID-19 regulations, and conforming to changing roles. In teaching, volunteering and assisting academics can play an important role in collaborating with students in solving exercises, providing additional examples, extending lectures beyond the syllabus but with relevant context, and sharing more course-related resources with students, in addition to higher OCB

levels academic staff tend to encourage collaborative research [9]. This demonstrates the importance of having and displaying OCB for teachers and schools because the teacher's function spans several levels and it is impossible to incorporate all of them into an objective job description [10]. Thus, OCB can be said to be discretionary behavior, not included in the formal job description, has a positive contribution to work and co-workers, shows active participation in work, thereby making a positive contribution to organizational performance.

Given that OCB is very important for teachers and has an impact on organizational effectiveness [11], organizational and individual performance [9], [12]–[14], and teachers' well-being [15], so it is important to understand the driving factors of teacher OCB. The purpose of this study is to analyze the influence of self-efficacy, intrinsic motivation, teacher engagement, and job characteristics on OCB. So that the school is able to encourage teachers to show high OCB in the school environment.

Previous researches [9], [13], [16]–[18] found that employee engagement is one of the antecedents of OCB, where employee engagement is a mental state that encourages a person to behave differently in operating his job effectively [17] and is closely related to innovative work behavior [19]. Meanwhile, Kwon and Kim [20] defines employee engagement as an active state of being fully self to bring something different at work, where job/personal resources of employees remain involved. Engaged employee feel that their job responsibilities are meaningful to themselves and the organization [17]. Engaged employees fill themselves with positive energy, thus engaging themselves energetically and vigorously in their work, leaving no time and space for negative thoughts to leave the organization [21]. On the other hand, Kwon and Kim [20] revealed that engaged employees are more likely to behave innovatively in response to obstacles by activating coping mechanisms, meaning that employee engagement and coping ability work together to support innovative behavior.

Teacher engagement is important not only for teachers but also for students, parents, schools, and the education system as a whole because they will do their jobs happily, are committed to the learning goals they set for their students, are enthusiastic about teaching and subject matter, persistent when faced with obstacles, pay attention to student' needs, and be absorbed in their work [22]. This is supported by previous research [23] who found, that lecturer engagement affects student engagement, which is also in line with another research [24], that who found that teachers are more fully involved in their work when they can involve students in learning. To encourage students to engage in learning, teachers must show high engagement. Bilal *et al.* [25] also found that all dimensions of teacher work engagement are related to student satisfaction with their teachers, so that the increased teaching services offered by highly engaged teachers are reflected in their dedication, which increases students' perceptions of satisfying learning experiences. In their research, Na-Nan *et al.* [17] concluded that employee engagement was a partial mediator between self-efficacy and OCB. Meanwhile, other study [26] found different results, where research on teachers at two secondary schools in the province of Nonthaburi, showed that OCB positively affected work engagement.

Previous studies [10], [17], [27]–[29] also found that teacher OCB is influenced by teacher self-efficacy. Self-efficacy reflects a person's belief in his ability to exert control over their own motivation, behavior and social environment [29]. An individual with self-efficacy beliefs shows a willingness to assume additional responsibility, perhaps because doing such activities can increase self-esteem [10]. A study by Musadad *et al.* [30] stated that self-efficacy is needed to face all challenges by showing teacher' beliefs, attitudes, and intentions about the need to achieve success in dealing with change. The personal efficacy of teachers largely depends on the amount of effort devoted to their teaching, decision-making abilities, and level of persistence in solving problems [28]. Using the term digital self-efficacy, Moreira-Fontán *et al.* [31] revealed that teachers with higher digital self-efficacy for teaching are more self-motivated and experience more intense enthusiasm, dedication, and absorption in their daily work. While employees with self-efficacy express determination, confidence, and motivation to work with organization [17], have greater cognitive resources, self-motivation and strategic flexibility to work in teams to ensure organizational success [29].

Paramasivam [27] conducted a study of 183 teachers from public and private engineering colleges in the southern part of India who were selected using purposive sampling technique, and found that teachers with higher levels of self-efficacy would feel that through their OCB to co-workers, students and institutions, they can make a difference on many levels. Meanwhile, Burić and Macuka [22] examined 941 teachers from various state schools in Croatia, and found that teachers with higher perceived self-efficacy, were more engaged in their work, experienced more joy, pride, and love, and less anger, burnout, and hopelessness towards their students [22], showing the competence of teachers in teaching [32], influencing the success and motivation of students [33]. However, Mahipalan *et al.* [10] shows that general efficacy does not affect OCB individual (OCB-I), but affects OCB organization (OCB-O), while personal efficacy affects OCBI and OCBO. OCBI benefits colleagues and indirectly contributes to organizational performance, whereas OCBO directly benefits the organization rather than the individuals [34]. Teacher self-efficacy is negatively related to stress and burnout [35], which shows that a higher level of self-efficacy reduces the stress and burnout experienced by teachers when carrying out their work. Teachers with higher self-efficacy beliefs report

higher ratings of closeness and lower ratings of conflict with students at all levels, building supportive and caring relationships with students [36]. This evidence shows that teacher' self-efficacy is very beneficial for students and organizations.

The decision to enter the teaching profession is influenced by extrinsic, altruistic, and intrinsic motives [37]. Teachers' perceptions of their work are very significant in influencing their OCB, so that more teachers perceive their teaching work as a profession and the center of their lives, as a source of satisfaction [3]. In their research, Pourtousi and Ghanizadeh [38] found that teacher motivation influences work engagement, although it does not mention the type of motivation influences it. Using a cross-sectional survey, the respondents included 324 full-time employees working in all hospitality establishments (i.e. coffee shops, restaurants, and hotel F&B departments) located in Seoul and Gyeonggi-do, South Korea, [39] concluded that intrinsic motivation appears to increase norms of reciprocity and organizational commitment, which in turn increases OCB. Meanwhile, research conducted by Lazauskaite-Zabielske *et al.* [40] on 884 employees from the Lithuanian public sector, revealed that prosocial motivation and intrinsic motivation predicted OCB and its dimensions, and intrinsic motivation moderated the relationship between prosocial motivation and OCB. However Christophersen *et al.* [41] who researched Norwegian preservice teachers, concluded that intrinsic motivation does not affect citizenship behavior. This research gap requires further research on the effect of intrinsic motivation on OCB, both directly and indirectly.

Research conducted by Shahid [42] revealed that engagement is influenced by freedom, a sense of autonomy, which has a positive effect on the overall well-being of employees, triggering higher motivation. This is in line with Kao *et al.* [43] who revealed that job autonomy is positively associated with work engagement. Meanwhile, using a different terminology, namely job characteristics, where it is revealed that job characteristics are predictors of employee engagement and job engagement found that job resources consisting of job characteristics, supervisor and co-worker support, participation in decision-making, and job security) are the key elements that affect work engagement [44]–[46]. On the other hand, Wan *et al.* [47] found that three job characteristics of task significance, job feedback, and skill variety were positively related to work engagement. This means that nurses tend to show high job involvement when they experience their tasks as having meaning and benefits, are provided with adequate information about their performance, and have the opportunity to use their skills [47].

An integrative literature review of 34 empirical studies shows that employees perceive high demands and resources as ideal for their engagement, innovative behavior is a consequence of smooth interactions, and engaged employees are more likely to behave innovatively by activating coping strategies to deal with challenges [20]. In addition, job demands also come from various sources and function both negatively and positively, while job resources train as a buffering effect to relieve stress from demands; individual coping strategies assist the demand process and potentially turn it into a source of greater achievement [20]. Tsigilis and Koustelios [48] found that cultivating positive perceptions about the significance of tasks allows teachers to realize that their efforts have meaningful consequences for the welfare of their students, families and society in general which in turn fosters their perseverance and strives to provide quality education. How teachers perform their duties, the meaning and significance of their tasks greatly affect students and are felt by families and society. Meanwhile, Sawalha *et al.* [49] found that job satisfaction moderates the relationship between job characteristics (feedback, task identity and task significance) and OCB (altruism and courtesy). Dixit and Upadhyay [19] found no relationship between job autonomy and employee engagement. Breevaart and Bakker [50] used the variable daily transformational leadership behavior to moderate the effect of daily challenging demands and daily hindrance demands on employee engagement, and found a significant effect. These findings reveal that the challenges, job demands and job resources encountered by the teacher will have an impact on how the teacher completes his work.

This research is important because it consider the lag experienced by students during the pandemic, is the problem found, which requires extra effort. This lag can be overcome by having OCB owned by teachers, so they are willing to behave outside their job description, to help students and colleagues to catch up. Currently, there is no empirical research on OCB in terms of teacher engagement as a mediating variable in the relationship between intrinsic motivation and self-efficacy towards OCB. In addition, researchers use job characteristics to moderate the effect of intrinsic motivation and self-efficacy on teacher engagement. This is a novelty in this research, in addition, this research was conducted on public elementary school teachers, especially during the post-pandemic period.

2. RESEARCH METHOD

This study uses a quantitative method, to examine the effect of intrinsic motivation, and self-efficacy on OCB mediated by teacher engagement and the moderating role of job characteristics on teacher engagement. OCB is measured by the dimension: altruism, civic virtue, conscientiousness, sportsmanship,

and courtesy, with a total of 11 questions. Intrinsic motivation is measured by the dimensions: competence, autonomy, connectedness, and workload, with a total of 13 questions. Self-efficacy is measured by the dimensions: efficacy for classroom management, efficacy for instructional strategies, and efficacy for student engagement, with a total of nine questions. Teacher engagement is measured by the dimensions of vigor, dedication, and absorption, with a total of 10 questions. Job characteristics are measured by the dimensions: task variety, task identity, task significance, and task autonomy, with a total of 10 questions. The subjects of this study were public elementary school teachers, in several districts in North Sumatra, Indonesia who had the status of State Civil Apparatus and Government Employees with Employment Agreements, totaling 20,188, which the researcher determined the sample using the Slovin formula, with an e value of 5%, it was obtained the number of samples is (1).

$$n = \frac{N}{1 + Ne^2}$$

$$n = \frac{20.188}{1 + (20.188 * 5\%^2)} = 392 \text{ respondent}$$

The research area consists of Langkat Regency, Deli Serdang Regency, Asahan Regency and Batu Bara Regency, Indonesia. The researcher randomly selected public elementary schools in the selected districts. Table 1 explains the number of samples per district in North Sumatra. The number of teachers with the status of State Civil Apparatus and Government Employees with work agreements in the selected schools was not large, therefore the researchers took all teachers with these statuses as a sample. Data collection was carried out by distributing questionnaires to research respondents. The instrument was created with a total of 53 questions using a Likert scale of 5 possible answers with a scale of five which includes: very agree=5, agree=4, less agree=3, not agree=2, strongly disagree=1.

Hypothesis testing was carried out with the help of the SmartPLS3 program, by conducting measurement model tests, namely testing the construct validity and reliability of each indicator. Next, we conduct a structural model test which aims to determine the effects that occur between the variables of this study. The proposed research hypothesis consists of (H1) intrinsic motivation has a significant effect on teacher engagement; (H2) self-efficacy has a significant effect on teacher engagement; (H3) teacher engagement has a significant effect on OCB; (H4) intrinsic motivation has a significant effect on OCB; (H5) self-efficacy has a significant effect on OCB; (H6) teacher engagement mediates the effect of intrinsic motivation on OCB; (H7) teacher engagement mediates the effect of self-efficacy on OCB; (H8) job characteristics moderate the effect of self-efficacy on teacher engagement; (H9) job characteristics moderate the effect of intrinsic motivation on teacher engagement; and (H10) job characteristics have a significant effect on teacher engagement.

Table 1. Number of samples per district

District/city	Number of public elementary school teachers	Number of samples	Participants
Langkat Regency	6,091	118	94
Deli Serdang Regency	7,716	150	108
Asahan District	3,843	75	54
Batu Bara District	2,538	49	29
Amount	20,188	392	285

3. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

3.1. Results

In total of 285 questionnaires were completed. The number of female teachers is 253 people (89%), more than male teachers, which is 32 people (11%). The age respondents consisted of 25 people 21 to 30 years (9%), 31 to 40 years 55 people (19%), 41 to 50 years 65 people (23%), and 140 people (49%) over 51 years old.

Validity and reliability tests were conducted on all research instruments, namely convergent validity consisting of loading factors, Cronbach's alpha, composite reliability, and average variance extracted (AVE). Based on the results of data processing, the loading factor value for all instruments is greater than 0.6, so it can be said that all instruments are valid. The AVE value from self-efficacy of 0.690, intrinsic motivation of 0.650, OCB of 0.679, teacher engagement of 0.621, and job characteristics of 0.690. The AVE value of all variables is greater than 0.5 therefore it can be stated that all variables have good convergent validity. Meanwhile, the value of Cronbach's alpha from self-efficacy of 0.943, intrinsic motivation of 0.954, OCB of 0.952, teacher engagement of 0.932, and job characteristics of 0.950. Meanwhile, the value of Cronbach's

alpha of all research variables is greater than 0.7, therefore it can be concluded that all research variables have good reliability. Composite reliability value of self-efficacy of 0.952, intrinsic motivation of 0.960, OCB of 0.959, teacher engagement of 0.942 and job characteristics of 0.957. The mark composite reliability of all research variables is greater than 0.7, therefore it can be concluded that all research variables have good reliability.

This study aims to examine the mediating role of teacher engagement in the relationship between intrinsic motivation and self-efficacy toward OCB and the moderating role of job characteristics in the relationship between intrinsic motivation and self-efficacy toward teacher engagement. The mediating variable used is teacher engagement, and the moderating variable used is job characteristics. Table 2 shows the summary of the proposed hypothesis testing. Table 2 shows that all proposed research hypotheses are accepted. Meanwhile, the indirect effect that occurs between the research variables is presented in Table 3. Table 3 shows that all hypotheses are accepted.

Table 2. Summary of hypothesis testing

	Original sample (O)	Sample means (M)	Standard deviation (STDEV)	T Statistics ((O/STDEV))	P values	Decision
Intrinsic motivation→OCB	0.240	0.250	0.076	3.161	0.002	Accepted
Intrinsic motivation→teacher engagement	0.370	0.368	0.071	5.208	0.000	Accepted
JC-IM→teacher engagement	0.218	0.218	0.087	2.506	0.013	Accepted
JC-SE→teacher engagement	-0.660	-0.659	0.098	6.726	0.000	Accepted
Job characteristics→teacher engagement	0.565	0.557	0.085	6.614	0.000	Accepted
Self-efficacy→OCB	0.435	0.425	0.081	5.380	0.000	Accepted
Self-efficacy→teacher engagement	0.339	0.348	0.092	3.670	0.000	Accepted
Teacher engagement→OCB	0.296	0.296	0.035	8.496	0.000	Accepted

Table 3. Indirect effects

	Original sample (O)	Sample means (M)	Standard deviation (STDEV)	T Statistics ((O/STDEV))	P values	Decision
Intrinsic motivation→teacher Engagement→OCB	0.109	0.108	0.022	4.904	0.000	Accepted
JC-IM→teacher engagement→OCB	0.065	0.065	0.027	2.359	0.019	Accepted
JC-SE→teacher engagement→OCB	-0.195	-0.196	0.038	5.132	0.000	Accepted
Job characteristics→teacher Engagement→OCB	0.167	0.166	0.036	4.707	0.000	Accepted
Self-efficacy→teacher Engagement→OCB	0.100	0.103	0.030	3.285	0.001	Accepted

3.2. Discussion

Organizational citizenship behavior can be explained as the teacher's extra-role behavior, in which the teacher will try to assist outside of the job description, outside of normal working hours, students and fellow teachers, to catch up on subject matter caused by online learning during the pandemic. This behavior is beneficial and supports the organization, which can reduce friction and increase efficiency, increasing the effectiveness of the organization [11], influencing individual and organizational performance [9], [12], [13]. Having OCB is very important for an organization to increase its effectiveness

The results of the study show that self-efficacy and intrinsic motivation affect teacher engagement. By having self-confidence and strong intrinsic motivation, teachers will be engaged with their work and organization. Lagging behind in learning materials during a pandemic is certainly a pressure for most teachers, but teachers certainly try hard so that their students can still achieve the required competencies. The current findings also suggest that teachers tend to be more engaged when they are working under certain job pressures, so it must be ensured that academics are constantly given assignments to complete within a limited time frame. Elementary school students who are still young with various backgrounds become a challenge as well as a demand for teachers, so being engaged will make it easier for them to accept and view this as fun. It becomes a pleasure and satisfaction when students can achieve competence when under the guidance of the teacher.

The results of the study show that intrinsic motivation, self-efficacy, and teacher engagement affect OCB. This supports the results of previous research, which found that employee engagement has a significant impact on OCB [16]–[18]. Engaged employees will be more involved and feel connected to work and the organization. Teachers with strong engagement with their organization and work will be able to show OCB

as a form of the extra role that is not listed in their job description. Because teachers who have high engagement will feel like an integral part of the organization and feel that what they do will contribute to the organization. Intrinsically motivated teachers engage in work because they find it interesting and satisfying, and may also seek to create a pleasant work environment so that they are more likely to help others and create a supportive work climate, in this way engaging in OCB. Likewise with self-efficacy, where the results of this study are in line with previous studies [10], [28], [29]. Teachers with higher degrees of self-efficacy believe that they can make a difference on many levels through their OCB with colleagues, students, and institutions [27]. Teacher self-efficacy varies, due to the teaching competence they have. Teaching competence can be shaped by years of work or experience, where the longer the teacher has been teaching, the more competence and self-efficacy will increase. Besides that, the decline in student interest in learning during the past pandemic, it will be the teacher's job to be able to increase it. Again, with various arguments, the teacher seeks to increase student learning motivation.

The results of the study show that teacher engagement mediates the effect of self-efficacy and intrinsic motivation on OCB. This means that self-efficacy will be able to influence OCB if it is mediated by teacher engagement. High self-efficacy leads to high teacher engagement, thereby increasing OCB. Often difficulties in implementing online learning previously reduced teacher confidence and confidence, coupled with the condition of students, in terms of motivation, ability to use technology, and ownership of technology that supports learning. OCB is a fundamental element in the teaching profession where teachers very often go beyond prescribed tasks [10]. When intrinsically motivated, the teacher's efforts are based on the enjoyment of the teaching task, which provides joy and pleasure to the teaching process.

Job characteristics moderate the effect of intrinsic motivation and self-efficacy on teacher engagement, where moderation in the relationship between intrinsic motivation and teacher engagement is positive, while the role of moderation in the relationship between self-efficacy and teacher engagement is negative. Job characteristics are very important for employees, especially teachers because they are a manifestation of a sense of creativity and innovation that arises in carrying out the learning process, especially in the post-pandemic period. The results showed that the higher the job characteristic will weaken the effect of self-efficacy and teacher engagement. This can be caused by even though teachers feel high job characteristics, but when facing gaps in student learning, teachers feel a weakening of engagement. It is understood that confronting gaps in student learning causes burnout for teachers and lowers engagement levels.

Self-efficacy and intrinsic motivation are important things for teachers to have in teaching elementary school students who still need a lot of guidance and direction. Teacher self-efficacy shows the teacher's readiness in dealing with classes containing many students with various backgrounds. This is not an easy thing, so it requires high teacher self-efficacy. Moreover, the challenges and problems faced during the past pandemic still overshadow learning activities. The teacher's intrinsic motivation is driven by the teacher's pleasure in doing his job. Teachers feel that they provide benefits to students and parents of students so that when they can teach and control the class well, the teacher feels pleasure, which goes beyond getting financial rewards.

The teacher is a special profession, requiring intrinsic motivation and self-efficacy in carrying out their duties. Demonstrating high OCB and engagement is an effort given to ensuring the achievement of learning objectives, especially in the post-COVID pandemic period which still leaves several problems. Job characteristics show how big the teacher's role is and the importance of the tasks they perform, and can strengthen employee engagement. In Indonesia, teachers are given the title of the unsung hero, which shows the amount of OCB shown by the teacher to educate his students.

4. CONCLUSION

Organizational citizenship behavior is particularly important for schools where the teacher's role spans many levels, and it is difficult to cover all of them in a job description, as the teacher's position is characterized more by discretionary responsibilities. For teachers, showing OCB to colleagues and students is very important, because teachers can be analogous to service work, which provides services to students and colleagues, even outside of school hours, where this certainly will not receive compensation. The results of the study showed that teacher engagement mediates the effect of self-efficacy and intrinsic motivation on OCB. The results of the study also showed that job characteristics play a role in moderating self-efficacy and intrinsic motivation in teacher engagement. The limitation of this research is that the research subjects are public school teachers with the status of State Civil Apparatus and Government Employees with Employment Agreements. So that in the future, research can be conducted in private schools. Future research can analyze aspects of age and years of service so that it can see differences in OCB based on the age and years of service of teachers.

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